

ISic0921

I.Sicily inscription 0921

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]Ε]λένην σύζυγον τὸν [---]

2. [---]γονον Θεόδωρον [---]

Apparatus

Text of IG

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492551

EDCS 39102078

PHI 140402

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0921. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI
edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4340076>